

Influence Of The Factors Of Business Opportunities Among Micro And Small Enterprises In Selected Areas Of Cavite

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Abstract

Micro and small enterprises provide employment opportunities, offer innovative environments for entrepreneurs to develop new products and services, and help people out of poverty. This study generally aimed to understand the factors of business opportunities that influence micro and small enterprises. The researchers employed descriptive-correlational research design and have used random sampling. This study selected 397 registered micro and small enterprises. Findings revealed that participants were mostly under sole proprietorship, having 1 to 9 employees with an estimated range of asset size of 3,000,000 pesos and operated within 1 to 3 years. Human capital (entrepreneurial knowledge by employees), social capital (communication with family and friends), and financial capital (invested additional funds for business operations) were the factors of business opportunities. Human, social, and financial capital were highly influential factors for business opportunities in micro- and small enterprises. Considerably, there was no significant relationship between the business profile of the participants and the degree of influence of factors of business opportunities, except with the number of employees and social capital. Thus, the researchers recommended that MSEs develop their entrepreneurial knowledge and skills, expand their business networks, and take advantage of financial institutions that offer lower borrowing fees.

Keywords: business opportunities, entrepreneurship, micro and small enterprises

1. INTRODUCTION

Micro and small enterprises (MSEs) significantly contribute to the economy, particularly in developing nations (Jalil et al., 2022). MSEs provided job opportunities, gave new and innovative places for entrepreneurs to learn, were seen as the source of new products and services, and helped get people out of poverty (Banupriya & Venkadesh, 2019). The majority of the enterprises in the Philippines are micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs), which comprise 99.51 percent of the total businesses in the country. Based on the data of the Department of Trade and Industry (2022), this population is composed of 90.54 percent micro-enterprises, 8.63 percent small enterprises, and 0.41 percent medium enterprises. Considerably, most of the MSMEs belonged to the wholesale, retail, and motorcycle industries. Most MSMEs are located in the National Capital Region (NCR), followed by regions 4A, 3, 7, and 6. The number of registered micro businesses in the Philippines has significantly increased over the past decade. These businesses include manufacturing, wholesale, retail, accommodation, food service, and retail (Department of Trade and Industry, 2022).

Njiraini (2018) asserts that age and firm size are two factors that affect how sound businesses take advantage of opportunities to innovate or grow. Other factors include employee backgrounds and education (Sebikari, 2019; Awtani & Millis, 2018), financial access (Njiraini, 2018; Ali, 2018 and Angeles, 2022), and social networks (Blankson et al., 2018 and Hatmawan, 2020). Micro and small business development and expansion are essential because they constitute the majority of commercial establishments in the country and fill in the gaps left by larger businesses by offering necessary goods and services. Moreover, it produces job creation and poverty reduction, contributing to the economy's growth. However, the potential of MSEs to exploit opportunities is hindered by the challenges they encounter. MSEs have a harder time accessing markets, getting financing, and taking risks on new products or business processes than bigger businesses (Tambunan, 2019 and Pardalis et al., 2019). Although micro and small businesses dominate the sector, the slow growth of these small businesses has remained a topic of discussion across many nations (Angeles, 2022). Additionally, market competition, lack of finances (Guevarra & Thiagarajan, 2019), and the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic have brought significant changes to the activities of businesses in the country, which has led to a significant decline in demand as well as a loss in income (Shinozaki & Rao, 2021). Some businesses have even been forced to shut down (Dagpin et al., 2022). The ability to maintain and sustain the operation of enterprises depends on how innovative the producers are and how flexible their strategies are executed (Malaluan, 2019).

Thus, the researchers aimed to understand the factors of business opportunities that influence the micro and small enterprises in selected areas of Cavite. This study may provide valuable information for micro and small enterprises, allowing them to scale up and expand their operations. Furthermore, this research could contribute to further developing entrepreneurial programs and policies for micro and small enterprises.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Business opportunities for micro and small enterprises

Given the current status of the globe and the need for continual development and expansion, micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) continue to grow. Entrepreneurs should launch an MSME firm because of its efficiency and appeal. Sebikari (2019) examined entrepreneurial capital, expertise, and capability as they relate to Ugandan small business performance. The study suggested that improving entrepreneurial performance can help SMEs achieve their goals. Considerably, entrepreneurial capital, expertise, and capability improve performance. Using social identity and social capital theories, Blankson et al. (2018) suggested that government agencies should support continuing programs and activities that aid small business owners, their employees, and the community by holding marketing seminars and talks. The study further revealed that social networks, customer and employee relationships, morality, and religion helped rural micro and small companies flourish in a competitive subsistence market.

Awartani and Millis (2018) analyzed the key factors impacting the expansion of MSEs. Through the binary logistic regression model, the study found that MSE development was mainly affected by the formality of enterprise registration, owner education, company industry, technology use, and age. Hatmawan's (2020) study showed that social capital significantly affects financial capital. Considerably, financial capital improves SME performance. SMEs with a high level of innovation can recognize, communicate, and coordinate with others, strengthening and building relationships with potential partners. SMEs with a high orientation toward entrepreneurship find better business opportunities because their limited resources require them to take advantage of all network-building opportunities. The study also found that the performance of SMEs improves in proportion to how well they manage their money and that entrepreneurs get better at managing their money as they make more connections in the community. However, Pardalis et al. (2020) found construction MSEs unprepared for innovation. The study found that one-stop-shop product-service system models can help MSEs offer comprehensive renovation packages instead of fragmented solutions. Due to perceived business risks, a lack of flexibility,

resources, and management competency, Swedish MSEs are not ready to coordinate such a concept.

2.2 Human capital in entrepreneurship

Human capital and experience in various fields determined the economy's competitiveness and modernization potential. Exploratory and confirmatory analyses were used to analyze the human capital's multidimensionality in SMEs' internationalization by the study by Dar and Mishra (2021). This study explained that practitioners learned how to assess human capital in SMEs by dimension from this study. Accordingly, policies and programs can be designed to enhance and develop human capital. Moreover, Kamal (2019) found that developing human capital improves workers' skills and experience. Human capital which includes knowledge, skills, expertise, aptitudes, attitudes, and other acquired traits, contributes to the production and gives an organization its unique competencies. Zainol et al. (2018) defined human capital investment as any action that improves workforce quality. Knowledge and training are needed to perform economic value-adding activities.

The study by Lee (2018) found that entrepreneurs' industry experience positively affected the entrepreneur's hard work, while their general education negatively affected it. The entrepreneurial effort also predicted venture success. Hard work also moderates the positive relationship between entrepreneur experience and venture success. Moreover, educators and policymakers may also design programs to increase the entrepreneurs' human capital value. Despite having sufficient resources, Ali et al. (2020) found that many businesses cannot build new products to meet customer preferences and market trends due to a lack of marketing capabilities, skilled marketing staff, and experienced managers. Intangible skills like intellectual capital, financial literacy, and business experience are essential in developing new products that promote sustainable competitive performance.

2.3 Social capital in entrepreneurship.

Prasetyo et al. (2020) examined how social resources and social capital drive business growth and competitiveness. The single-track model showed that economic structures, job opportunities, economic development, human capital, and social capital positively and significantly increase firm competitiveness. The dual-track model showed that human resource skills drive remarkable economic growth and social capital competencies boost entrepreneurial competitiveness. Ali and Yousuf (2019) examined how social capital affects entrepreneurs. The study found that social and community capital's

four variables positively affect an individual's perceived self-efficacy and entrepreneurship desirability, which boosts business intentions. Cofré-Bravo et al. (2019) looked at farmer support network social capital. Fresh fruit exporters, who must innovate in production, were studied. Farmers' support networks use all three types of social capital: bonding, bridging and linking. Bonding and bridging social capital have advantages and disadvantages in a business cultural network. It also showed that bonding social capital could mobilize resources for new projects. However, it may limit the firm's access to innovative ideas, while bridging social capital can identify more new opportunities but may struggle to exploit new ideas. The interaction of bonding and bridging social capital creates innovation, which contributes differently (Ceci et al., 2019).

2.4 Financial capital in entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurs need money to seize opportunities and expand. Without financial resources, entrepreneurs struggle to start and grow a business (Abiodun & Amos, 2018). Angeles (2022) explained that external financing increases capital for business investment, while internal financing limits microenterprises' growth opportunities and makes them focus on staying in business. Business owners don't want to borrow money and prefer internal financing. Considerably, Cole and Sokolyk (2018) further explained that startups with better performance prospects use debt, particularly business debt. Debt-based startups are more likely to survive and grow three years after launch than equity-based ones. Debt obtained in the name of the firm is associated with longer survival times and higher revenues.

In contrast, debt obtained in the name of the firm's owner does not affect on survival times and is associated with lower revenues. Jalil et al. (2022) found that microfinance services are crucial to MSE growth. The study found that microfinance services boost MSE growth. Microfinance services boost MSE growth by improving social and psychological capital. Based on the study of Tjandra et al. (2022), asset tangibility, firm age, and leverage negatively affect working capital, while profitability and growth opportunities positively affect it. Working capital is unaffected by operating cash flow or firm size. In addition, working capital financing affects profitability, according to Setiantio (2022). Better financial infrastructure let companies use more short-term debt without hurting profits.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1 Research Design

The researchers utilized a descriptive-correlational research design in conducting this study. The descriptive design was used to describe the business profile of the participants, the factors of business opportunities, and their respective degrees. Considerably, the researchers utilized correlational design to determine the significant relationship between the business profiles of the participants and the degree of influence of the factors of business opportunities.

3.2 Sources of Data

The study utilized both primary and secondary data sources. Primary data were acquired from the responses of the participants using self-structured survey questionnaires via Google Forms which was validated and tested for reliability. In addition, secondary data were gathered from published online journals, books, and other academic sources online to support and strengthen the study.

3.3 Sampling Design

The study's target population was 397 registered micro and small enterprises (MSEs) in the Department of Trade and Industry- CALABARZON (IVA), Cavite. The researchers employed a random sampling technique in selecting the participants of the study. The researchers solely used micro and small enterprises in the respective cities and municipalities whose managers or store owners were the participants. The researchers used Slovin's formula to identify the sample size of the study.

3.4 Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers utilized MSEs in Cavite, registered under the Department of Trade and Industry Region IV-A. In the process of data gathering, the researchers contacted the Department of Trade and Industry-IVA for a list of MSEs in selected Cavite areas, including Rosario, Cavite City, Tanza, General Trias City, Trece Martires City, Kawit, Bacoor City, and Imus City. It was then advised to get to contact and request assistance from each city and municipality's Local Government Unit-Business Licensing Office (BPLO). The researchers used online google forms to distribute and for the retrieval of data upon the approval of the request and consent to conduct the survey.

3.5 Research Instrument

The researchers utilized a self-constructed survey questionnaire as a research instrument in the collection of data using Google Forms, a web-based survey application. The research instrument underwent content validation from experts in related fields to test its validity and reliability. Cronbach alpha value is calculated at 0.78.

3.6 Statistical Treatment

The researchers used frequency count and percentage to determine the participants' business profiles and the factors of business opportunities. The Likert scale was also used to determine the degree of influence of the factors of business opportunities. Lastly, Spearman rank correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the business profile and the degree of influence of the factors of business opportunities of the participants.

3.7 Research Framework

The study used the conceptual framework as shown in figure 1. The framework shows the process of conducting this study. Firstly, the researchers determined the business profile of the participants, the factors of business opportunities, and their degree of influence through descriptive research design. In addition, an inferential analysis of the relationship between the business profile and the factors of business opportunities was provided through the use of a correlational research design. Finally, the researchers utilized the analysis of data, interpretation, and discussion to generate a conclusion and formulate recommendations and business insights that may serve as the catalyst for the entrepreneurial development and upscaling of MSEs.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of understanding the influence of the factors of business opportunities of micro and small enterprises

3.8 Ethical Consideration

The participants were informed by the researchers that their participation was completely voluntary, unpaid, and open to withdrawal at any time. The participants signed a consent form to proceed with completing the survey questionnaire. The confidentiality of participants was protected by the anonymity of the completed questionnaires, which were used solely for research purposes. Moreover, conducting this study guaranteed that no human rights were violated.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Business profile of the participants

Table 3 exhibits the type of ownership of the participants that responded to the study. It shows that 85.39 percent of enterprises are operating under sole proprietorship. Considerably, enterprises operating under corporations have the least percentage of 1.01 percent. The results implied that most of the micro and small enterprises in selected areas in Cavite operate with sole ownership. This is parallel with the findings of Barbosa (2021) and Dagpin (2022), which found that sole proprietorship was the common type of business organization.

Table 3. Forms of business organization of the participants

Forms of Business Organization	Frequency	Percentage
Sole proprietorship	339	85.39
Partnership	49	12.34
Corporation	4	1.01
Cooperative	5	1.26
Total	397	100.00

Table 4 shows the range of the number of employees of the participants. It depicts that 96.47 percent are nine employees and below, and 3.53 percent are 10 to 49 employees. This reveals that most of the participants belong to microenterprises considering the number of employees they have. According to the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI)(2022) and Senate Economic Planning Office (SEPO)(2012), businesses with one to nine employees are classified as microenterprises. This conforms with the general population of MSMEs in the country, which noted that businesses were dominated by microenterprises (DTI, 2022; Shinozaki & Lakshman, 2021).

Table 4. Number of employees of the participants

Number Of Employees	Frequency	Percentage
1 to 9 employees	383	96.47
10 to 49 employees	14	3.53
Total	397	100.00

Table 5 showcase the business profile of the participants in terms of length of operation. As shown, 40.30 percent of the participants have been operating for one to three years. In addition, MSEs operating within seven to nine years has the least percentage of 7.05 percent. It indicated that two-fifths of the micro and small businesses operate for one to three years. This also demonstrates that numerous establishments opened for business when the province's quarantine and lockdown were lifted. This conforms to the study of Shinozaki and Rao (2021), which indicates businesses began to recover and adapt to the new normal setting, which includes contactless and digital transactions, one year after the pandemic outbreak. Moreover, Dagpin et al. (2022) validate that the majority of the business in selected areas in Cavite, Philippines, has been in operation for between two and five years.

Table 5. Length of operation of the participants

Length of Operation	Frequency	Percentage
One year below	87	21.91
1 to 3 years	160	40.30
4 to 6 years	63	15.87
7 to 9 years	28	7.05
Ten years above	59	14.86
Total	397	100.00

Table 6 presents the business profile of the participants in terms of the range of asset size. As shown, 95.47 percent of MSEs have an estimated asset size range of P3,000,000 and below. Moreover, the range from P3,000,000 to P15,000,000 has the least percentage of the total responses, 4.53 percent. This indicates that most MSEs have an asset size of P3,000,000 and below. Additionally, the capitalization range of P3 million and below falls under micro enterprises as defined by the DTI (2021) and SEPO (2012) under RA 9501: Magna Carta for MSEs. Furthermore, the result is parallel with the findings of Shinozaki and Rao (2021) and Table 4, which characterized microenterprises as the dominant result.

Table 6. Range of asset size of the participants

Asset Size	Frequency	Percentage
P3,000,000 and below	379	95.47
P3,000,001 to P15,000,000	18	4.53
Total	397	100.00

4.2 Factors of business opportunities

Table 7 showcase the factors of business opportunities in terms of human capital. It shows that 19.28 percent of the total responses answered entrepreneurial knowledge possessed by employees. Considerably, other responses from the participants have the least percentage of 0.33, which include integrity of employees, willingness and commitment to learning by both employer and employees, training, and proper wages with benefits". Generally, the majority of the participants consider that the entrepreneurial knowledge of employees could help them to develop and upscale their businesses. This conforms to the study of Sebikari (2019) and Kamal (2019) that entrepreneurial knowledge improves the performance of small enterprises.

Table 7. Factors of business opportunities in terms of human capital

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Educational attainment of employees	180	11.93
Entrepreneurial knowledge possessed by employees	291	19.28
Entrepreneurial experience of employees from their previous work	221	14.65
Entrepreneurial skills possessed by employees	213	14.12
The loyalty of employees to the business	260	17.23
Providing technology and etiquette training for the employees	131	8.68
Taking care of the physical and mental health of employees	208	13.78
Others	5	0.33
Total	1509	100.00

Table 8 presents the factors of business opportunities in terms of the social capital of MSEs in selected areas of Cavite. As shown, 34.50 percent of the responses are about communicating with family and close friends to adopt and use new technologies and practices. On the other hand, another response has the lowest percentage of 0.12 percent, which include "providing good service always that could be a good marketing tool by word of mouth to client's friends, family, and acquaintances ."The result shows that communicating with family and close friends to adopt and use new technologies and practices could help MSEs to develop and upscale their businesses in terms of social capital. Consequently, the result supports the findings of Ceci et al. (2019) that innovation is the result of the interaction between bonding and bridging capital, and each contributes uniquely to the final outcome. It concluded that bonding and bridging capital are essential to the success of the innovation process. Moreover, in the study of Prasetyo et al. (2020), social capital competencies are a key factor in increasing business competitiveness.

Table 8. Factors of business opportunities in terms of social capital

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Communication with family and close friends to adopt and use new technologies and practices.	286	34.50
Building relationships with strangers or with social	268	32.33

groups by attending events and joining the association to learn about new information and resources.		
Interaction with government officials.	93	11.22
Communicating with individuals using social media.	181	21.83
Others	1	0.12
Total	829	100.00

Table 9 demonstrates the factors of business opportunities in terms of financial capital. It shows that 46.20 percent of the responses invested additional funds for business operations. Considerably, other responses have the least percentage of 1.32 percent, which include "own savings," "loans from family," "revolving funds from income," and "funds from their friends and families ."It indicates that investing additional funds for business operations could help MSEs to further develop and upscale their business. In accordance with the findings of Angeles (2022), business owners only use internal finance since they are hesitant and unwilling to borrow money. Moreover, in the Vietnamese context, the study of Nyanamba (2019) indicated that SMEs still do not make use of loans.

Table 9. Factors of business opportunities in terms of financial capital

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Getting loans from banks and other financial institutions.	173	25.29
Invested additional funds for business operations.	316	46.20
Investment of funds to short-term securities.	72	10.53
Issuance of share capital to investors.	57	8.33
Selling of liquidated assets to gain additional funding.	57	8.33
Others	9	1.32
TOTAL	684	100.00

The table presents the mean value of the degree of influence of the factors of business opportunities. It shows that a mean value of 4.51 on human capital is Highly influential. Likewise, the social capital of the factors of business opportunities has a 4.48 mean value which is Highly influential. Similarly, a mean value of 4.64 on financial capital with a descriptive value of Highly influential. In general, all factors of business opportunities, such as human capital, social capital, and financial capital, were highly

influential in accordance with the corresponding responses of the participants. The result parallels the study of Khan et al. (2019) and Hatmawan (2020) that social and financial capital contribute significantly and positively to the performance of businesses. However, Khan et al. (2019) disapprove that human capital significantly influences the performance of businesses. This demonstrates that human capital is not the primary factor that drives the development of enterprises.

4.3 Degree of influence of factors on business opportunities

Table 10. Degree of influence of the factors of business opportunities among the participants

Category	Mean	Descriptive Value
Human capital	4.51	Highly influential
Social capital	4.48	Highly influential
Financial capital	4.64	Highly influential

Table 11 showcase the correlation of forms of business organization of the participants to the factors of business opportunities. The results show human capital has a positive, very weak correlation with the type of ownership with a coefficient value of 0.029, while both social capital and financial capital showed a negative, very weak correlation with a coefficient value of -0.046 and -0.035. Moreover, the results imply that human capital, social capital, and financial capital had no significant relationship to the forms of business organization of the participants, hence, accepting the null hypothesis.

4.4 Correlation of business profile and degree of influence of business opportunities

Table 11. Correlation between type of ownership and degree of influence of factors of business opportunities

Category	Coefficient	P-Value	Description	Significance
Human capital	0.029	0.566	Positive Very Weak Correlation	Insignificant
Social capital	-0.046	0.361	Negative Very Weak Correlation	Insignificant

Financial capital	-0.035	0.492	Negative Very Weak Correlation	Insignificant
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*Significant values set at 0.05 critical level

Table 12 demonstrates the correlation between the number of employees of the participants and the factors of business opportunities. The findings reveal a coefficient value of 0.024, 0.134, and 0.082 that corresponds to a positive, very weak correlation between all factors of business opportunities and the number of employees of the participants. However, the results indicate that only social capital has a significant relationship to the number of employees of the participants with a p-value of 0.008, hence, rejecting the hypothesis. This means that the higher the number of employees the enterprises have, the higher chances of developing social capital. According to Lukiyanto and Wijayaningtyas (2020), social capital reduces the need for equity despite the difficulties businesses face in obtaining venture capital by trying to imitate their predecessors, borrowing business needs, and assisting one another in reducing business operations, including labor assistance. Moreover, Ceci et al. (2019) support that bonding and bridging social capital are both useful for businesses to get the resources they need for new projects and in finding more new access to take advantage of business opportunities.

Table 12. Correlation between the number of employees and degree of influence of factors of business opportunities

Category	Coefficient	P-Value	Description	Significance
Human capital	0.024	0.641	Positive Very Weak Correlation	Insignificant
Social capital	0.134	0.008	Positive Very Weak Correlation	Significant
Financial capital	0.082	0.101	Positive Very Weak Correlation	Insignificant

*Significant values set at 0.05 critical level

The table presents the correlation of the length of operation of the participants to the factors of business opportunities. The findings reveal that all factors of business

opportunities, such as human capital, social capital, and financial capital, have a positive, very weak correlation with a coefficient value of 0.025, 0.017, and 0.08, respectively. Moreover, the results show an insignificant relationship between the factors of business opportunities and the length of operation of the participants, thus, accepting the hypothesis.

Table 13. Correlation between length of operation and degree of influence of factors of business opportunities

Category	Coefficient	P-Value	Description	Significance
Human capital	0.025	0.613	Positive Very Weak Correlation	Insignificant
Social capital	0.017	0.736	Positive Very Weak Correlation	Insignificant
Financial capital	0.098	0.052	Positive Very Weak Correlation	Insignificant

*Significant values set at 0.05 critical level

Table 14 showcases the correlation between the estimated range of asset size and the factors of business opportunities, such as human capital, social capital, and financial capital. The results imply that all factors of business opportunities have a positive, very weak correlation towards an estimated range of asset size of the participants with a coefficient value of 0.040, 0.025, and 0.086, respectively. Moreover, the results show that all factors of business opportunities have no significant relationship towards the estimated assets size of the participants with a p-value of 0.422, 0.621, and 0.088, hence, accepting the null hypothesis.

Table 14. Correlation between the estimated range of assets size and degree of influence of factors of business opportunities

Category	Coefficient	P-Value	Description	Significance
Human capital	.040	0.422	Positive Very Weak Correlation	Insignificant
Social capital	.025	0.621	Positive Very Weak	Insignificant

			Correlation	
Financial capital	.086	0.088	Positive Very Weak Correlation	Insignificant

*Significant values set at 0.05 critical level

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

After the data facilitation, processing, analyses, and discussions, the researchers conclude the following:

1. The MSEs in selected areas of Cavite were dominated by microenterprises. These enterprises are commonly in sole proprietorship type of business ownership; they have 1 to 9 employees with an estimated range of assets size of P3,000,000 and below, and operating within 1 to 3 years.

2. The factors of business opportunities in terms of human capital are: educational attainment of employees, entrepreneurial knowledge possessed by employees, the entrepreneurial experience of employees from their previous work, entrepreneurial skills possessed by employees, the loyalty of employees, providing technology and etiquette training for the employees, and taking care of the physical and mental health of employees. Entrepreneurial knowledge of the employees dominated the factors of business opportunity in terms of human capital. In addition, factors of business opportunities in terms of social capital are communication with family and close friends to adopt and use new technologies and practices, building relationship with strangers or with social groups by attending events and joining the association to learn about new information and resources, interaction with government officials, and communication with individuals using social media. Communication with family and close friends to adopt and use new technologies and practices dominated the factors of business opportunity in terms of social capital. Moreover, factors of business opportunities in terms of human capital are: getting loans from banks and other financial institutions, investing additional funds for business operations, investment of funds in short-term securities, issuance of share capital to investors, and selling liquidated assets to gain additional funding. Invested additional funds for business operations dominated the factors of business opportunities in terms of financial capital.

3. The level of influence of the factor of business opportunities in terms of human capital, social capital, and financial capital was highly influential to the development and upscaling of MSEs.

4. There was no significant relationship between the business profile of MSEs and their degree of influence on the factors of business opportunities such as human capital, social capital, and financial capital, excluding the correlation between the number of employees and the degree of influence of social capital, which has correlated significantly.

Based on the results of the study, the researchers recommend that the MSEs must develop entrepreneurial skills, expand their business network, and use low-cost financial institutions. Moreover, providing and enhancing more entrepreneurial training and seminars will strengthen the entrepreneurial knowledge of MSEs in Cavite. This could also help MSEs build social networks. Policymakers should implement policies and incentives for new entrepreneurs, MSE development, and MSE capital access. The researchers also recommend exploring other variables that influence MSEs' business opportunities. Future researchers could include the industry sector in profiling due to the fact that business opportunity factors vary by industry, educational attainment, and age of entrepreneurs. They could also investigate the challenges MSEs face and their intentions for business development.

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